

Global economic impacts of Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza: A systematic review and impact framework

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ABSTRACT

Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI) has risen globally since the early 2000s, causing economic impacts on industries, government, ecosystems, and society. A systematic literature review (SLR) following PRISMA guidelines was conducted to document and quantify the economic and financial impacts of HPAI. Data on economic methods, impact parameters and control strategy assessments were extracted. Impact estimates were converted into 2024 values and expressed as impact per agricultural GDP, per capita and average annual income. A framework categorising impact types was developed and quality was assessed using an adapted Consolidation Health Economic Evaluation Reporting Standards (CHEERS) protocol. Eighty-five papers covering 27 countries and 14 methodological approaches were analysed. Financial losses ranged from \$1.14 million in USA, New York (1925) to \$3881.87 million in Nigeria (2014–2016), with the later representing 0.43% of agricultural GDP, or \$4.14 per person or approximately 280,000 annual incomes. Control strategies evaluated include vaccination, regionalisation, pre-emptive culling, surveillance, trade restrictions and bird housing orders. The framework identifies 135 impact parameters affecting the poultry industry, government, public health, other businesses and environment. Across all sectors direct costs dominate the literature, while direct consequential costs, indirect consequential costs and non-financial impacts remain relatively underexplored. Substantial quality variability was found with critical gaps in data transparency, incomplete costs and lack of standardisation of methods. This framework provides a vital comprehensive structure for future economic assessments, facilitating cross-study comparisons, enabling cost-benefit analyses of control strategies, and supporting more informed policy and investment decisions.

1. Introduction

Avian influenza viruses have circulated and evolved globally for over six decades, posing major global health challenges and disrupting economies (Duan et al., 2023). Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI) strains have led to high mortality in domestic and terrestrial populations like breeder, layer or broiler chickens (APHA, 2025). Within aquatic, wild birds and some domestic birds (e.g. Anseriformes, waterfowl, shorebirds etc) the virus is often asymptomatic and they act as reservoirs which facilitate the spread of the virus to susceptible

populations through contaminated water and environment (Tripathi et al., 2025). Recently, in the spring of 2024, an unprecedented cross-species spillover of H5N1 was reported in dairy cattle in USA, increasing concerns of increased risk to humans (USDA, 2024; Uyeki et al., 2024). Such zoonotic events have already been reported in 954 people between 2003 and 2024, with 464 of them dying (WHO, 2023). Influenza's ability to mutate, sustain transmission outside of avian hosts and create a pandemic is a major concern (WOAH, 2025).

HPAI has far-reaching impacts across public health (Peiris et al., 2007), farming (Barnes et al., 2024), food systems (Leibler et al., 2009),

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businesses, and both national and global economies (Rushton et al., 2005; Elçi, 2006; Humphries-Waa et al., 2013; Robert et al., 2016; Cakir et al., 2017; Fasanmi et al., 2018). Controlling and eliminating the virus in poultry production requires major investments by producers, governments, and communities such as testing, culling, vaccination, and improved biosecurity (Nielsen et al., 2023). As such, the disease has caused the culling of millions of birds worldwide. While these actions generate financial losses to farmers, they also disrupt supply chains, international trade, threatening livelihoods and reducing food security (FAO and WOA, 2025). In severe epidemics, poultry and poultry products supplies have been reported to plummet causing a sharp increase in product price to consumers (Thompson et al., 2019). Within international trading channels, importing countries may impose export bans and trade restrictions on areas affected by HPAI, causing revenue losses (Yalçın, 2006; Paarlberg et al., 2007; Akunzule et al., 2009; Longworth et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2016). Consumer demands have been reported to be volatile during outbreaks due to disease scarce. In addition, the disease has been reported to cause important environmental impacts apart from the costs and losses associated to human health cases.

Despite the important financial impact generated by HPAI and the growing literature on economic impact studies, to date no comprehensive framework has yet been presented that captures the variety of impacts across human, animal, environment, food, and economic domains for HPAI. No review has been conducted to understand the disease impact across countries globally. A framework developed by Dijkhuizen and Morris (1997) provides an integrated and economic reasoning, through an economic model, whilst considering animal welfare and farm profitability. The model has limitations like context sensitivity and the use of real-world data. A review by Otte (2008) focused on production impacts in low-middle-income countries (LMICs) but remained siloed in that it considered economic impact of livestock production without considering the larger context or elements of interconnectedness between systems. Narrod et al. (2012) presented an integrated epidemiological and economic framework for assessing zoonoses using a “one health” concept with cross-sector economic impact of zoonoses using modified risk analysis and different analytical tools. The framework aimed to link outputs of animal and human models, economic impact models and the risk management to improve strategies; though this is very generic and uses costs very loosely. Saatkamp et al. (2016) developed an impact framework for non-communicable neglected diseases but does not provide details specifically for avian influenza.

An overview of the total impact of HPAI and a framework that integrates all types of HPAI impacts as they affect different groups in society is desirable (Smith et al., 2019) to understand the full consequences of this virus. Such information can be helpful for researchers and decision-makers to understand where problems occur, magnitude, gaps and actions required for data improvement, knowledge, preparedness, risk communication, food systems risk management, trade, and social vulnerabilities. The aim of this study was to conduct a systematic literature review to document and quantify the economic and financial impacts of HPAI globally, the economic impact of control strategies used and to inform the development of an impact framework for HPAI. The research questions were: 1) What types of financial impacts of HPAI have been estimated in the literature?; 2) What are the type and pattern of financial and non-financial impacts HPAI generates across different sectors, regions and society?; 3) What are the reported financial and non-financial outcomes associated with different HPAI control strategies?; and 4) What are the methodological approaches used to estimate these impacts?

2. Material & methods

2.1. Search strategy

The SLR was conducted using the Preferred Reporting Items for

Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. The protocol used in this review was registered in Prospero (CRD42024522239), before data extraction.

An initial search was performed in PubMed, Web of Science and CABI Digital Library, using a variety of search terms to warrant inclusivity of articles. The search was restricted to articles published from the 1st of January 2000, onward. Key sentinel papers were identified and used to assess the appropriateness of the proposed search terms. Based on this, the final set of search terms, outlined in Table 1, were reviewed and approved by the study’s co-authors. A final search was performed on the 30th of May 2025 across PubMed, CABI Digital Library, Web of Science, and Google Scholar.

Due to the considerable number of articles retrieved from Google Scholar (30,000 articles), only the first twenty pages (200 articles) were included based on recommendations in the literature: Hughes et al. (2014) and Roe et al. (2014) stated that screening the first 10 pages of Google Scholar results (i.e., approximately 100 records) is generally sufficient to capture the majority of relevant studies. Haddaway et al. (2015) recommended a screening threshold of 200–300 records to better capture grey literature. A midpoint threshold of 200 records was used.

For all other databases, all retrieved references were included for screening. The final search results from all four databases were exported to Microsoft Excel, where duplicates were automatically removed using formatting tools. A manual check was conducted to identify any remaining duplicates.

2.2. Screening and article selection

Articles were screened using a two-step process. Initial screening was done by reviewing the titles and abstracts, followed by full-text screening of selected articles. During the full-text review, reference lists of the selected papers were also examined to identify further relevant articles not captured in the original search. The screening criteria are presented in Table 2.

Three co-authors participated in the article selection process. To ensure consistency; the first author and one co-author independently

Table 1
Keywords inputted into search engines and databases.

PubMed	((High Pathogenic Avian Influenza) OR (HPAI) OR (High Pathogenic Avian Influenza Virus) OR (HPAIV) OR (Highly pathogenic notifiable avian influenza)) AND ((economic) OR (finance*) OR (cost*) OR (monetary) OR (pecuniary) OR (commercial) OR (budgetary) OR (fiscal) OR (loss*) OR (expense) OR (expenditure) OR (consequence*) OR (influence) OR (implication*) OR (ramification) OR (repercussion*) OR (impact*) OR (effect*))
CABI Digital Library	[[All: "high pathogenic avian influenza"] OR [All: hpai] OR [All: "high pathogenic avian influenza virus"] OR [All: hpaiv] OR [All: "highly pathogenic notifiable avian influenza"]] AND [[All: economic] OR [All: finance*] OR [All: cost*] OR [All: monetary] OR [All: pecuniary] OR [All: commercial] OR [All: budgetary] OR [All: fiscal] OR [All: loss*or]] AND [[All: expenditure] OR [All: expense*] OR [All: consequence*] OR [All: influence] OR [All: implication*] OR [All: ramification*] OR [All: repercussion*] OR [All: impact*] OR [All: effect*]]
Web of Science	"High Pathogenic Avian Influenza" OR HPAI OR "High Pathogenic Avian Influenza Virus" OR HPAIV OR "Highly Pathogenic notifiable avian influenza" (Topic) AND "economic" OR "finance*" OR "cost*" OR "monetary" OR "pecuniary" OR "commercial" OR "budgetary" OR "fiscal" OR "loss*" OR "expenditure" OR "expense" OR "consequence*" OR "influence" OR "implication" OR "ramification" OR "repercussion" OR "impact*" OR "effect*" (Topic)
Google Scholar	"High Pathogenic Avian Influenza" HPAI "High Pathogenic Avian Influenza Virus" HPAIV "High Pathogenic Notifiable Avian Influenza economic finance* cost* monetary pecuniary commercial budgetary fiscal loss* expenditure expense* impact* consequence* influence implication ramification repercussion effect*

Table 2
Inclusion and exclusion criteria for screening database search articles.

Inclusion	Exclusion
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peer-reviewed scientific articles Grey literature sources including, reports and government, international organization, and institutional articles Articles evaluating the non-monetary and monetary quantifiable impact of HPAI which goes beyond the scope of costs Articles examining changes in Socioeconomic Status (SES) due to HPAI outbreaks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trials or causation studies Articles not providing specific information on HPAI Articles only looking at impact of Avian Influenza (AI) at the genomic, cellular, or physiological level (non-population studies) Articles only focusing on the epidemiological impact in the poultry sector without addressing economic or social impact Risk factor studies Literature and systematic reviews lacking economic analysis context No relevance to economic implications

screened 10% of the articles at the title and abstract stage. The screening results by both authors was then compared, and a 96.9% agreement was observed. Due to this high agreement percentage between authors, it was deemed acceptable that the lead author carry out the rest of the title and abstract screening independently. In cases where eligibility was unclear, these were reviewed collaboratively with co-authors and decisions were made by consensus. The full-text screening was carried out by the lead author, with any doubtful papers reviewed again jointly with co-authors to decide whether to include them or not in the review.

During title and abstract screening, sixteen non-English articles were identified; however, fifteen had English-language abstracts and were excluded at this stage as irrelevant. During full-text screening, one non-English article was classified as having insufficient clarity based on abstract-level information and therefore underwent full-text translation using the ChatGPT-4o (Omni) model. These articles were assessed against the study's inclusion and exclusion criteria and were subsequently excluded. ChatGPT-assisted translations were used as a secondary validation step to ensure that the full texts of non-English articles did not omit critical cost data or impact outcomes relevant to the study.

2.3. Data extraction

The type of data extracted from each article is shown in [Table 3](#).

This approach allowed authors to comprehensively assess each study's context and content, allowing a critical understanding of the methods and findings. Data on disease impacts were categorised based on whether they belong to five sectors: Poultry Industry, Government, Public health, Other businesses and Environment. Impacts within the poultry industry were those affecting all business involved in production and processing of poultry and poultry products up to the retail level and associated inputs. This includes businesses (including individual entrepreneurs) such as poultry farms, poultry feed suppliers, slaughterhouses, hatcheries, egg packing stations, poultry transporters, amongst others.

Table 3
Description of the data extraction.

Category	Description
Study information	- Type of article - Study design - Year of publication - Journal in which the article was published - Peer-reviewed status - Type of virus - Aims of the study - Control strategy used
Methods	- Continent, country, region - Economic context - Period of analysis - If the study was a simulation study - Description of epidemiological parameters - Financial method and parameters - Data collection details - Sensitivity analysis - Animal population
Results	- Type of production system and species - Level of disease impact - Currency used in the study - Parameters most impacted - Main conclusions
Discussion	- Main recommendations - Major assumptions and limitations

All costs related to human health disease impact and associated expenditures (e.g. cost of healthcare) were classified within the Public Health sector, even if some of these are government costs.

Impact parameters identified within each sector were subsequently organised following the framework developed by [Saatkamp et al. \(2016\)](#) on the categorisation of economic impacts of outbreaks of highly contagious livestock disease. The framework was adapted to include cost due to disease in animals (e.g. revenue forgone from mortalities) and the non-financial costs ([Table 4](#)). Quantitative estimates on disease impacts for each sector and overall were extracted together with the denominators used to measure the impact.

The data extraction process was piloted with the help of co-authors. Piloting involved two co-authors extracting data using [Table 4](#) and then comparing their extracted information. This was to provide multiple perspectives and to ensure the extraction form is comprehensive and for quality assurance.

2.4. Quality assessment

The quality of the articles included was evaluated using 27 parameters. These were based on [Compston et al. \(2022\)](#) who used a 42-parameter framework that was adapted from the Consolidation Health Economic Evaluation Reporting Standards (CHEERS) ([Husereau et al., 2013](#)) to fit economic impact studies. For this study, the parameters selected were based on their relevance to the economic burdens posed by HPAI outbreaks. The focus was on assessing the overall quality, relevance, and transparency of economic studies of HPAI. It examines the study's context, population, methods, data sources, and assumptions, as well as how economic impact is measured and interpreted. Consideration is also given to result clarity, relevance to stakeholders, and whether conclusions align with findings.

A point-based system was used where a point was given for each quality parameter that was met by the study. Scores produced were analysed through descriptive statistics. No article was excluded from the analysis based on this quality assessment, as the purpose was to determine the quality of the articles and not to inform their inclusion.

Table 4
Type of costs associated to disease impact [adapted from [Saatkamp et al. \(2016\)](#)].

Type of cost	Definition
Direct costs (DC)	Costs 1) related to the effect of the disease in animals (e.g. losses in performance and death); 2) related to measures aimed at controlling and eradicating the HPAI virus on the affected farm (e.g. culling of live birds.); or 3) losses incurred by business directly linked to the infected farms.
Direct consequential costs (DCC)	Costs of control measures aimed at preventing further virus spread to unaffected poultry holdings and related businesses. These include the losses or costs of businesses located within the movement restriction zones (MRZs) (e.g. cost of movement license) or holdings outside the movement restriction zone that are impacted by the outbreak (e.g. reduce slaughtering by slaughterhouses).
Indirect consequential costs (ICC)	Costs of market effects during the outbreak, which could affect the poultry supply chain (e.g. changes in consumptions or poultry meat prices, or losses in trade) or other non-poultry sectors (e.g. changes in prices of alternative proteins or losses in tourism).
Aftermath costs (AC)	Costs that occur after eradication of the virus and lifting of all restriction measures (e.g. repopulation of breeding stock previously culled or the costs associated to reestablishing exports markets).
Non-financial impacts (NFI)	All impact that could not be quantified financially (e.g. stress). Measures such as DALYs are considered financial measures and are placed within the above categories.

2.5. Data analysis

A descriptive analysis summarized the key characteristics of the included studies.

2.5.1. Quantifying the economic impact

To quantify the economic impact the total costs were extracted from the articles where available. To allow comparisons between regions and context, four common denominators were selected: 1) Agricultural Gross Domestic Products (AgGDP), 2) National annual average income (NAI) 3) Per capita and 4) Cost per poultry. The \$ sign is used in the results to indicate USD.

Using the official exchange rate during the period of analysis (Local Currency Unit (LCU) per US\$, Period average) the total HPAI impact extracted were converted to USD (World Bank 2025). If the period of analysis (*t*) spanned multiple years, an average exchange rate was calculated and used. The impacts were converted from local currency into USD (\$).

To calculate present values of the impact, inflation from study period (*t*) to the year 2024 was calculated using the consumer price index for each country published by the World Bank (2010 =100). If the period of analysis spanned multiple years, the last year of the analysis period was selected World Bank (2025b). The 2024 present value (PV) of HPAI impact, was then calculated impact of disease was multiplied by the inflation as shown in Eq. 1.

$$PV\ Impact = (Impact\ in\ USD_t) * (1 + Inflation_{t-2024}) \quad (1)$$

The impact of HPAI as percentage of AgGDP was calculated to obtain a comparable measure of the importance of the impact relative to the agricultural economy of each country. This was estimated by dividing the original impact estimated by the AgGDP of the respective study period and multiplied by 100. Data on AgGDP was sourced from World Bank (2025c). If the study's analysis covered multiple years, the aggregate AgGDP values for those same years were used.

The HPAI impact per NAI was used to compare the relative significance of HPAI across countries with varying economic levels, particularly between high-income countries (HICs) and LMICs. It indicates how many individual annual incomes could have been paid with the value of the total cost of the disease. This was calculated by dividing the HPAI impact extracted for the study period by the NAI countries reported for the same period, which was sourced from World Bank (2025d). If the period of analysis spanned multiple years, the NAI of the latest year of analysis was used.

The HPAI impact per capita was deemed a useful measure to adjust the impact estimates to the population size of the country or region. It indicates the average cost of the disease per person in the country. This was calculated by dividing the present value of the disease impact by the national population. National population was extracted from World Bank (2025e).

The HPAI impact per bird represents a relative measure of the impact to the size of the poultry industry in a country. The poultry population was obtained from either FAO estimates or from the studies, when available. It was calculated by dividing the present value of the impact by the total poultry population estimate of the study period.

2.5.2. Development of HPAI impact framework

An HPAI economic impact framework was created to describe and categorise the different types of impacts and their parameters. Economic parameters were constituted as variables used or proposed to estimate impact. The structure of the framework was based on the economic impact categories shown in Table 4 (as adapted from Saatkamp et al. 2016) and the type of sectors the parameters were associated with (Table 5).

Grouping of impact parameters was done through a process of structured categorisation and refinement, where parameters were

Table 5
Description of sectors in HPAI economic framework.

Sector	Definition
Poultry industry	Encompasses economic parameters related to private actors in the poultry and related agricultural sectors, including poultry farms, hatcheries, slaughterhouses, input suppliers, and related infrastructure and service providers.
Government (agriculture and veterinary)	Comprises parameters related to public agricultural and veterinary institutions, including government ministries, national veterinary authority and their field services and associated bodies and infrastructure, including regulatory bodies and government laboratories.
Public health	Involves parameters related to the public health sector at all levels spanning public (e.g., government) and private actors (e.g., households) and including everything from system-level expenditures to societal impacts and increased demands on services.
Other businesses	Captures the more hidden economic impacts on private actors of non-agricultural sectors affected by HPAI outbreaks. This includes businesses such as insurance providers, tourism operators, transportation, retail, and food services.
Environment	Includes parameters related to the environment, particularly wildlife populations, biodiversity, land use, and natural resource

repeatedly compared against the framework, assessed for overlap or ambiguity, and reorganised to ensure conceptual clarity. This involved identifying redundancies, merging overlapping categories, and creating new ones when impacts did not logically fit within existing groups.

A coding system was generated to classify economic parameters by country income level (HICs/LMICs), poultry species and its validity (empirical, theoretical, or recommended cost) (Table 6). This was done to allow filtering for aspects of interest, such as specific contexts, poultry species, or empirical studies. Countries were categorised in accordance with World Bank classification by income (World Bank, 2022). The number of studies that include each impact parameter was also indicated to provide insight into the extent of research coverage on these parameters.

2.5.3. Narrative synthesis

A narrative synthesis was conducted using the four steps of the framework by Popay et al. (2006) to analyse systematically the economic impacts of HPAI across sectors and income contexts. The first step of the Popay framework, i.e., establishing a conceptual model of how

Table 6
Coding framework for classifying economic parameters by context, species, and data source.

Code/Category	Description	Purpose in framework
HICs	High-income countries	Identifies if the parameter was derived from data in a high-income setting.
LMICs	Low- and middle-income countries	Identifies if the parameter was derived from data in a lower-or middle-income setting.
Species-specific tag	Indicates which poultry species the parameter applies to (e.g., broiler, layer, duck, turkey).	Ensures species relevance and avoids overgeneralization of impacts.
E	Empirical (historical outbreak assessment)	Shows that the cost is based on actual outbreak data.
B	Benefit	Indicates a cost was beneficial to the area of society.
T	Theoretical simulation model	Indicates that the cost was derived from a model or hypothetical outbreak scenario.

HPAI generates cascading economic impacts was done through the development of the HPAI impact framework. In the second step, the relationship exploration phase, patterns and relationships within and between these groupings were examined through textual descriptions and tabulation, identifying recurring findings across studies while highlighting impacts unique to specific contexts or regions (when found). In the third step, exploring relationships in the data, the influence of factors such as income context, geographic region, and outbreak characteristics on the magnitude and distribution of economic impacts were identified. In the final step, the robustness assessment, the quality and strength of evidence, consistency of findings and sensitivity to study design and bias including potential reviewer assumptions were reflected on. Key findings were summarised in narrative style.

3. Results

3.1. Results of the articles selection process

The initial search returned 7779 papers of which 2617 were duplicates and removed. A further 4806 were excluded with the large majority (62%) being genomic, cellular, or physiological studies of HPAI. After full-text screening, 59 studies remained for data

extraction. An additional 26 studies were located through reference lists resulting in a total of 85 studies included in this review (Fig. 1). Articles included are listed in [supplementary file A](#).

3.2. Descriptive summary

Articles included described the impact of HPAI in 27 countries, although some described the impact for one territory and six studies focused on global HPAI impact (Fig. 2). The top research-producing countries on HPAI impact were the United States of America (USA) (20), Nigeria (9) and Vietnam (6). The most researched continents were Asia (33) and North America (21)), followed by Africa (15), Europe (14)

Oceania (1) and South America (1).

Table 7 shows an overview of the characteristics of the studies included. Most studies used data between 2005–2008 and were published in 2006, 2009 and 2010 and looked at multiple species simultaneously (broilers, layers, turkeys were mentioned the most). In several studies, poultry was referenced without clearly specifying the species analysed.

3.3. HPAI financial impact estimations

Table 8 provides an account of the economic disease burden based on historical HPAI epidemics. The analysis reveals substantial financial burden of outbreaks, depending on geographic context, scale, and the structure of the poultry sector. Studies differed greatly in terms of methods used, the type of parameters considered and the level of analysis (e.g., industry, sector, government).

In LMICs, a range of outbreak scales and responses were described. For example, Vietnam and Indonesia demonstrated a shift in control response from a culling-based approach in 2004 (which cost \$ 686 million to Vietnam and \$1.14 billion to Indonesia) to a vaccination strategy in 2005 that allowed reducing DC (Rushton et al., 2005; Mcleod et al., 2007). In African LMICs, smaller-scale outbreaks with high response costs were described. For example, Nigeria experienced recurring outbreaks starting as early as 2006 (Fasina et al., 2008; Fadiga and Okike, 2012) with economic consequences such as market price disruptions and delay in compensation issues. In the case of China (Qi et al., 2014), the large economic impact in poultry was derived from closure of live poultry markets. Hence, in majority of studies from LMICs there was a focus on how to reduce government expenditures, while maintaining disease control and preventing the collapse of formal and informal poultry production and markets. In contrast to HICs studies that considered DCCs, LMICs studies offered limited economic detail beyond compensation and culling costs.

In European contexts, publish economic impact studies relate to

Fig. 1. Flow diagram illustrating the number of articles identified, excluded and includes.

Fig. 2. Geographic distribution of articles included in the analysis.

Table 7
Study characteristics from the 85 articles.

Study area	Characteristic	No. studies	Study area	Characteristic	No. Studies	
General aim	Economic impact	37	Virus subtype	H5N1	49	
	Market and trade dynamics	18		H5N2	3	
	Intervention and control	13		H5N1&H5N2	1	
	Policy and knowledge	11		H5N2&H5N8	1	
	Surveillance, prevention, and response	6		H5N8	1	
Article type	Original article	62		H7N1	1	
	Review article	13		H7N3	1	
	Peer-reviewed magazine	5		H7N4	1	
	Conference proceeding	2		H7N7	1	
	Short communication	2		H7N9	1	
	Working paper	1		Not specified	28	
	Scientific journal article	64		Species	Multiple species	38
Publication type	International organisation report	10			Broiler	7
	Report	6			Layers	7
	Government report	4	Egg production		4	
	Book chapter	1	Turkeys		3	
Study design	Simulation	38	Terns		3	
	Historical-case study	30	Gulls		2	
	Observational	9	Native Birds		2	
	Retrospective	5	Ducks		1	
	Case-control	3	Peruvian pelicans		1	
Context	High-income	38	Ostriches		1	
	Middle-income	33	Harbour seals		1	
	Upper-middle-income	14	Great Skua		1	
	Regional	43	Northern Gannet		1	
Level of impact	National	33	Geese	1		
	International	9	Eagles	1		
	Unspecified	3	Not specified/applicable	14		
	Local	1				
	Peer-reviewed	Yes	68			
No		16				
Unclear		1				

early start of HPAI epidemics in 1999 and 2003, while more recent studies focused on hypothetical impact and control of HPAI. Overall a stronger emphasis on government-led eradication programmes was observed including stamping-out to protect supply chain infrastructure and maintaining international trade and export markets. Early detection alongside strict biosecurity have been a routine control tool.

The USA provides the largest number of impact estimates, including more recent outbreaks incursions in 2015. Their impact studies focused on government-controlled mass culling and regionalisation, however

they often consider effects beyond the poultry industry. Ripple effects on consumers constituted 82% of the total costs in the 1983–1984 Pennsylvania outbreak (Halvorson, 2009) or was reported as a major cost in the 2015 turkeys outbreaks in Minnesota, Iowa, South Dakota, and Wisconsin (Cakir et al., 2017). One study (Decision Innovation Solutions, 2015a), quantified the impact of outbreaks to collateral sectors, such as the feed industry, estates, petroleum refineries, and concluded that these ‘indirect costs’ were higher than direct costs in poultry. Several studies also provided impact insights related to federal and state

Table 8
Economic burden of HPAI based on historical HPAI outbreaks presented in chronological order.

Country and time period considered	Total impact (million US \$)	Epidemic size	Economic parameters used	Biggest contribution to total impact
United States (New York) 1924- 1925	1.41	Culling of 500-600 thousand chickens.	Details not provided	Details not provided
United States (Pennsylvania) 1983-84	1241.65	Culling of 17 million birds from 448 flocks.	Stamping out costs and losses, and extra costs to consumers	82% are extra costs to consumers.
Australia (New South Wales) 1997	3.42	Outbreaks affecting 2 commercial broiler breeders (farm sizes were 128,000 and 32,000 birds) and an emu and broiler growing farm (n = 261 emus).	Destruction of birds and eggs and compensation.	48.7% of total costs attributed to compensation
Italy 1999	891.60	Impact of involving 413 outbreaks and the culling of 16 million birds.	Government expenditures (including compensation, culling, costs of materials and vaccination) and farmers' loss (loss of income, non-recoverable fixed costs, loss of eggs and meat and pay to workers).	77.9% of costs accounted for industry losses
Belgium 2003	55.99	Culling of 147 farms and 189 hobby herds (2.3 million birds destroyed).	Eradication and compensation costs	Details not provided
Netherlands 2003	381.79	Culling of 30 million birds.	Direct losses covering the value of the culled herds, the organizational costs and the overhead costs.	Details not provided
Canada (British Colombia) 2004	448.81	42 commercial poultry farms affected, and more than 17 million birds culled.	Farmers losses, compensation costs and losses due to unemployment and reduce demand.	41% losses from unemployment and lack of demand for services. 16.7% of costs due to compensation.
Indonesia 2004	1140.23	Culling (including death) of 16.2 million birds.	Direct farm costs (details not provided) and indirect costs (control and eradication costs).	67% of costs were indirect losses
Japan 2004	11.93	Culling of 283,534 birds from 4 farms.	Costs of depopulation of farms and compensation.	69% of costs were compensation costs
Thailand 2004	3578.24	Culling of 63 million birds.	Loss to broiler farms, hatcheries, feed mills, slaughterhouse and exports.	Biggest losses on slaughterhouses (29%), broiler farms (29%) and export market (24%)
Vietnam 2004	686.04	Culling of 43.2 million birds.	Direct losses (details not provided)	Details not provided
Cote d'Ivoire 2005	34.55	Vaccination of 31.8 million birds.	Vaccination costs (vaccine, vaccinators, cold chain, equipment and transport), post-vaccination monitoring, communication and government staff costs.	85% vaccination costs. 53% towards public sector costs. 67% vaccination costs. 63-69% vaccination costs. 82% towards public sector costs.
Indonesia 2005	2.04	Vaccination of 6.43 million birds.		
Vietnam 2005	66.52	Vaccination of 364.5 million poultry.		
Kenya 2005	129.18	No details provided. Based on extrapolations of 319 households with poultry and 155 poultry businesses survey following HPAI consumer fear.	Reduction of flock sizes, premature selling of birds, cancelation of day-old chick, reduced production of day-old chicks at hatcheries and reduced demand for products.	Mainly due to reduced demand of poultry products
Türkiye 2006	3362.48	Culling of 16 million hens (including surveillance zones) from 230 outbreaks.	Production losses, impact of market prices, loss of management fees and government costs for disease control and compensation.	42% due to losses in market prices for broilers. 14% expenditure on disease control cost to government.
Nigeria 2006	586.31	Outbreak resulting in compensation paid to farmers for 1.89 million birds.	Direct costs (bird mortality and value loss of chicks in breeders), indirect costs (loss due to reduced egg price and mortality), consequential costs (culling, restocking and downtime), compensation and government budget allocations.	76% accounted for indirect costs.
Nigeria 2006-07	50.27	Culling of 1.9 million birds in 97 states.	Compensation costs	Compensation costs.
Ghana 2006-07	111.02	35 million birds affected across 80 farms and 22 live bird markers country wide.	Government costs (prevention, equipment, cleaning and disinfection, transportation, surveillance, staff time, sampling and diagnostic, and compensation) and industry costs (revenue loss from dead birds and eggs loss or change in prices, and biosecurity)	45% due to government expenditure.
Türkiye 2006-07	226.52	Culling of 14 million birds.	Government subsidies to farmers	Government subsidies.
Türkiye 2006-07	721.43	No details provided. Estimation of impact for the contract broiler industry.	Producers' losses in income and loans taken	Details not provided.
Nigeria 2006-10	568.40	Culling of 1.3 million birds.	Direct costs (chicken death and egg losses, costs of control, culling, surveillance and vaccination) and indirect costs.	Details not provided.
South Africa 2011	13.27	Culling of 34 Ostrich farms leading to 37,000 birds and 3000 eggs.	Compensation costs	Compensation costs only.
China 2013	2188.09	131 poultry cases (farms) confirmed in 10 provinces; 121 human cases.	Losses due to live poultry market closure, culling of birds and human cases (medical costs and DALYS based).	56.9% of impact towards poultry (no further detail provided).
India (Kerala) 2014	2.04	18,544 cases leading to the culling of 0.277 million poultry birds in 288 farms.	Government costs of compensation, culling, monitoring and surveillance.	89.4% compensation costs
United States of America (Iowa) 2014	1648.44	30 million layers/pullets and 1.5 million turkeys in Iowa affected.	Direct effects (costs of supplies and equipment); indirect effects (costs to suppliers and vendors); induced effects (incomes losses from household purchases).	36% attributed to indirect effects

(continued on next page)

Table 8 (continued)

Country and time period considered	Total impact (million US \$)	Epidemic size	Economic parameters used	Biggest contribution to total impact
United States of America 2014	3447.20	38 million layers and pullets affected.	Direct effects (producers), indirect effects (supply chain), the induced effects on household income loss and tax implications.	48% attributed to indirect effects
United States of America 2015	297.78	7.33 million infected commercial turkeys in Minnesota, Iowa, South Dakota, and Wisconsin.	Estimation based on producer supply and consumer demand losses.	92% of costs due to trade export losses
United States of America (Iowa) 2014-15	1163.34	Culling of 50 million birds.	Government costs for outbreak and fall planning activities (compensation, response activities on premises, fall planning costs and overtime, travel, and supplies for veterinary services' employees).	69% towards response costs 23% compensation expenditures
United States of America 2015	1376.43	7.5 million turkeys and 42.1 million egg layers and pullet chickens affected.	Welfare producer losses in poultry and other livestock and feed sectors and losses in land value- and value-added products.	68% losses to U.S. livestock and feed producers and processors.
Nigeria 2014-16	3881.87	Culling of 2.7 million birds in 465 outbreaks.	Direct costs (bird dead, culled and eggs destroyed), indirect costs (replacement value and downtime effect), compensation and feed costs saved.	47.8% from loss of potential eggs
Nigeria 2014-17	191.57	Culling of 779 farms affected and 3.7 million birds.	Birds culled, dead, egg destroyed, feed destroyed, losses in egg production and compensation paid.	61% from culling birds

level tax. Overall, USA studies reveal a significant focus on avoiding disruptions to the supply chain and negative effects on society (i.e. consumer and unemployment).

3.3.1. HPAI impact per AgGDP, NAI and capita

Fig. 3 shows the HPAI impact as a percentage of AgGDP and per capita. The epidemic in Kenya (2005) and Thailand (2004) was found to account for a large proportion of AgGDP, 43.4% and 15%, respectively. Analysis on effect per capita shows Thailand (2004) and The Netherlands (2003) had the highest impact, with disease costing an average of \$37 and \$15 per person. Most estimates showed that HPAI cost less than \$4 per person in the population. Outbreaks in LMICs countries impose a larger relative burden on agricultural GDP, but HICs

bear larger absolute losses, with a more widely documented distribution of costs among producers, consumers, and governments.

Fig. 4 shows the value of total cost of HPAI in terms of number of average incomes. Based on this measure, the three countries experiencing the highest impact were Thailand, Nigeria and China with HPAI impact equivalent to approximately 445,000, 280,000 and 233,000 incomes, respectively.

3.3.2. Impact on prices

Several studies reported a temporary fall in poultry and egg prices due to HPAI outbreaks, although few provided statistical evidence of the attribution of HPAI to price changes. The Turkish marketing sector reported a 31% decline in broiler meat prices, while egg prices fell by up to

Fig. 3. HPAI outbreak impacts as a percentage of agricultural GDP (left) and economic impact per capita (right).

Table 9
Economic analyses of HPAI control strategies based on simulations.

Country and time period considered	Control strategy	Reference
USA (2001-04)	Impact of regionalization in the event of HPAI outbreaks.	(Paarlberg et al., 2007)
Belgium (2003)	Three control scenarios: 1) stamping-out, 2) emergency vaccination and 3) combined strategies	(Vandendriessche et al., 2010)
Belgium (2003)	Two control strategies: 1) Stamping out and 2) Emergency vaccination (within 1-5 km if infected premise).	(Vandendriessche et al., 2009)
The Netherlands (2005- 09)	Two strategies: 1) EU baseline strategy and 2) EU baseline strategy + culling in 1 km radius	(Meuwissen et al., 2006)
Vietnam (2005-10)	Two vaccination strategies: national vaccination program and targeted vaccination program based on water bird density, chicken density, elevation, and land use/land cover.	(Tran et al., 2016)
The Netherlands (2006)	Eight control strategies: (1) EU baseline strategy, (2) 72-h standstill and pre-emptive depopulation within a 1- or (3) 2-km radius of detected farms; (4) Vaccination in 3 and (5) 10 km zone; (6) vaccination and depopulation within a 1 km radius of detected farms; (7) preventive vaccination in High and medium density areas and depopulation within 1 km radius of infected farms; and (8) depopulation within 2 km radius in high density areas.	(Longworth et al., 2014)
Nigeria (2006-10)	The compare actual impact under intervention done with impact without no intervention. The intervention was a multisectoral national control program implemented through the <i>Avian Influenza Control Project (AICP)</i> , financed via a World Bank IDA loan of \$50 million (with \$41 million disbursed over 2006–2010). The four scenarios were 1) low number of cases and disease burnt out; 2) low number of cases and disease becomes endemic; 3) high number of cases and disease burnt out; and 4) high number of cases and disease become endemic.	(Fadiga and Okike, 2012)
Nigeria (2007)	Vaccination over the course of 3 years, with 70% coverage of the country.	(Fasina et al., 2007)
The Netherlands (2008)	Five control strategies: existing EU strategy (baseline); Pre-emptive culling of all AI susceptible birds in a radius of 1 km (Cul1), 3 km (Cul3) and 10 km (Cul10) around infected flocks; and emergency vaccination of all flocks except broilers, in 3 km radius (Vac3) around infected flocks.	(Backer et al., 2015)
USA (2012)	To compare the current strategy with the same strategy plus vaccination. The current approach includes depopulation, surveillance, and quarantine: infected flocks are stamped out,	(Egbendewe-Mondzozo et al., 2013)

Table 9 (continued)

Country and time period considered	Control strategy	Reference
	premises disinfected, nearby flocks are tested weekly, and affected areas are quarantined. The alternative strategy adds vaccination to this existing approach.	
United Kingdom (2020-22)	Housing order for commercial free-range egg layers.	(Barnes et al., 2024)
USA (2022-23)	Trade restriction bans and heat restriction to control HPAI using data with a heat exemption.	(Padilla et al., 2025)
Indonesia (West Java) (2023)	Two strategies in a 3,000-broiler farm: early selling of birds, and stamping out	(Gumilang et al., 2022)

efficient, estimating \$4.18 billion (Oladokun et al., 2012; Fasanmi et al., 2018). A general intervention and surveillance package applied during 2006–2010 had variable cost-effectiveness depending on disease dynamics; under endemic conditions with high mortality, the intervention was marginally more economically efficient presenting a benefit-cost ratio of 1.75 over the course of 5 years, but not under lower-mortality or burn-out scenarios; whereby the infectious reach saturation and there are no more subjects to infect (Fadiga and Okike, 2012).

In Vietnam (2005–2010), a targeted vaccination program based on environmental and poultry density risk mapping reduced losses by 52.2% compared to no intervention, outperforming the blanket national campaign (33.1% reduction in losses), underlining the efficiency gains of spatial risk-based approaches (Tran et al., 2016).

Overall, vaccination was seen as a most-cost effective and accepted control measure in LMICs. This was not the case in HICs (The Netherlands and Belgium) as the costs of vaccination was significantly high due to extra surveillance requirements in vaccinated flocks.

3.3.4. Economic impact of reported on public health

Two studies included economic analysis of public health consequences due to HPAI. Qi et al. (2014) investigated the H7N9 epidemic in China estimating a cost of \$2.19 billion, including indirect losses from human illness like medical costs and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). The total cost of DALYs corresponded to \$6.4 million for a total of 121 patients. Humphries-Waa et al. (2013) assessed the Cambodian perspective of HPAI in humans between 2005 and 2011. The total economic burden of H5N1 cases was \$11,200, with an average cost of \$299 per patient, largely borne by medical providers.

3.4. Impact Framework

Table 10 summarises the number of economic impact parameters associated with impacts across different sectors. Across all sectors, three major patterns emerge:

- Direct costs dominate the literature while direct consequential costs and indirect consequential costs remain underexplored. DC represent a third of all parameters.
- Non-financial impacts receive minimal attention, except in relation to public health impact. These are mostly captured in LMICs studies due to virus infection found in humans.
- Methodological approaches dramatically vary by sector, limiting comparison. See Section 3.5.

Government impacts show the most balanced distribution across all cost categories. Whilst environmental sector remains the most understudied sector with some parameters identified and rarely quantified.

Table 10
Total number of impact parameters across different sectors.

Sectors	No. of parameters	Direct costs	Direct consequential costs	Indirect consequential costs	Aftermath cost	Non-financial impacts
Poultry industry	44	20	4	7	11	2
Government (agriculture and veterinary)	33	12	9	3	7	2
Public health	41	8	2	6	2	23
Other businesses	11	5	0	2	4	0
Environment	6	0	1	2	1	2
<i>Low- middle- income countries</i>	117	41	12	16	22	26
<i>High income countries</i>	80	36	11	16	14	3
Total	135	45	16	20	25	29

3.4.1. Poultry industries

Poultry industry section exhibits well documented parameters across all cost categories, dominating the framework with 33% of all parameters identified (Fig. 5). The DC parameters span from different types of sunk costs due to poultry sickness to revenues foregone and expenditures for disease control. The loss due to death and culling in many studies was combined in an overall loss parameter. This lack of differentiation was also reflected in estimates of compensation payments, as farmers are usually not compensated for the birds who have died from the disease, just those culled. Exceptions were: i) on the 2006–2007 HPAI outbreak in Ghana, described a total production loss for farms based on the number of birds that died naturally (Akunzule et al., 2009), ii) a study from Türkiye that mentioned how many birds died from the disease (Yalcin et al., 2009); and iii) a study from Nigeria that reported 223,000 chickens death due to H5N1 infection (Diao et al., 2009). The latter two did not estimate the value of these birds that died.

Various types of parameters were investigated as DCC, spanning both legal and illegal activities including the effects of movement restrictions. In the USA, a major cost incurred by poultry operations was the acquisition of movement permits to support business continuity and mitigate

operational disruption. During the 2015 HPAI outbreak, approximately 7800 movement permits were issued, facilitating around 20,000 intra- and inter-state movements as of April 2016 (Thompson and Pendel, 2016). While non-essential movements were restricted, permitted essential movements helped reduce business disruption. However, the permitting process required additional biosecurity measures, including enhanced equipment cleaning, disinfection, and security protocols. The study in Kenya, on 319 households, found 72% broiler farmers and 52% of layer farmers reported cancelling of orders for day old chicks (Omiti and Okuthe, 2009) resulting in business lost for the hatcheries of 3202, 950 Kenyan Shillings (US\$ 24,777.48).

The ICC parameters include extra costs to producers, costs due to foreign trade changes and revenue forgone due to restrictions. Several of the ICC parameters suggested fluctuations towards informal or illegal trading markets. In Vietnam (2012–2013), trade of sick or dead animals was mentioned by 47 poultry farmers across Hai Duong, Dong Nai and Long An. In Hai Duong, 17 broiler chicken farmers indicated that sick broilers above 1 kg would sell at 33.3–83.3% of the market price. Whereas in Dong Nai, 10 farmers suggested the sick dead birds were sold to rear reptiles at 10–20% of the market price. Farmers in other

Fig. 5. Details a section of the economic framework which categorises the impacts into direct costs, direct consequential costs, indirect consequential costs, aftermath costs, and non-financial impacts of the poultry industry. It highlights the range of losses faced by producers, industry, production losses, disease control expenditures, trade disruptions, livelihood impacts, and long-term effects on genetic diversity and compensation issues*: T: Theoretical, E: Empirical, * LMIC only, ** HIC only. DOC=day-old-chicks.

provinces mentioned the sick birds were slaughtered and prepared for human consumption (Delabouglise et al., 2016). Farmers anticipated that the notification of outbreaks will drop poultry prices, due to movements restrictions, consumer demand fear, the oversupply generated by large number of farmers selling their birds to avoid infection and the opportunist behaviour of traders. Thus, this trade is seen as advantageous towards poultry trader and slaughter due to an increase profit margin through lower priced purchasing and selling at normal market prices. A study conducted in Kenya investigated losses related to slaughter behaviour (Omiti and Okuthe, 2009). It found that among households affected, 25% of farmers reported panic-slaughter of their flocks with broiler farmers more willing to cull birds prematurely, likely due to market specifications for minimum slaughter weight.

Aftermath Costs spanned many contexts where studies reported losses in income, job or business. In Türkiye, several medium-scale, semi-integrated, and integrated firms became bankrupt after the 2005–2006 outbreak (Yalçin, 2006). Another study by Yalçin et al. (2009) found 62% of producers who had planned business expansions postponed or decided against future investment due to outbreak-related uncertainty. In Africa there were estimated job losses for farmers, traders and middlemen (Guèye, 2007) which directly impacted local communities member’s livelihoods. In Ghana, 2006–2007, there was a reductions in sales income of 39% from reduced flocks and reduction of household income of 31%, (Akunzule et al., 2009). Thailand showed structural changes as autonomously owned and operated enterprises were replaced by contract farming due to the technological innovations like evaporative cooling systems which sped production and improved bird survival (Safman, 2009). The cost of these new technologies was typically shared between the parent company and the contracting producers for whom adoption of this technology this was a precondition for retaining their contract.

Dissatisfaction with government was a commonly expressed NFI. In Iran, a lack of assurance regarding government compensation was reported Fallah Mehrabadi et al., (2021) with farmers sending live turkeys to slaughterhouses immediately after observing poultry deaths on their farms. Authorised poultry farms were guaranteed government compensate for their losses due to HPAI as follows; layers (\$2.03),

broiler (\$3.30), breeder (\$6.00), turkey (\$25.35), backyard chicken or duck (\$4.60) and embryonic egg (\$0.40). However, compensation totalled to 75% of the value of the birds, litter, and animal products that were destroyed. Therefore, incomplete compensation and delayed payment led to dissatisfaction among farmers.

3.4.2. Government impacts

Fig. 6 shows the impact parameters for the agricultural and veterinary government authorities. The studies reviewed tend to concentrate heavily on expenditure related to disease control and compensation, and to a lesser degree on preventive measures associated with contingency planning, such as biosecurity and surveillance. This emphasis suggests a largely reactive, rather than proactive, governmental approach.

Studies analysing government cost were found to be very restrictive to few parameters, generally omitting many of the key critical expenditure and losses incurred. Some studies focused mostly on expenditures related to bird depopulation, highlighting it as one of the major costs. In Belgium 2003, the government was estimated to have paid \$4.30 per bird for culling, transport and destruction, (Vandendriessche et al., 2010), while in Nigeria (2014–17) these represented 61% of all government expenditures. Compensation payment was a key focus in several studies, and the sole focus of investigation for those done for Nigeria 2006, Türkiye 2006–07, South Africa (2011) epidemics. For other studies, the cost of compensation ranged from 16% (Canada 2004) to 69% (Japan 2004) of all government costs. Some other studies were centred on vaccination costs, presented in the framework as DCC. Studies done estimate the cost of vaccine at \$0.21 per dose in Italy (2010), \$0.04 in Nigeria (2000–2008) and \$0.06 in Vietnam (2007), with transactional costs of vaccination generally ignored (Fasina et al., 2007; Mcleod et al., 2007; Sartore et al., 2010).

Few studies mentioned the importance of fixed costs on infrastructure and preparedness, such as upgrading of laboratory infrastructure required to support enhanced diagnostic capabilities. Hinrichs and Sims (2006) reported that in Thailand, approximately \$1 million was invested in laboratory upgrades. Similarly, in Hong Kong, new laboratories were established with an estimated investment of HKD 47 million (approximately \$6 million), largely driven by avian influenza preparedness

Fig. 6. Details a section of the economic framework, which categorises the impacts into direct costs, direct consequential costs, indirect consequential costs, aftermath costs, and non-financial impacts of the government. This includes expenditures on outbreak control, compensation, vaccination, licensing, biosecurity, and preparedness, as well as wider societal impacts such as reduced GDP, loss of social cohesion, decreased education access, and diminished trust in government. T: Theoretical, E: Empirical, R: Recommended, * LMIC only, ** HIC only. GDP=Gross Domestic Product.

needs. In Vietnam, around \$340,000 was allocated for upgrading laboratory information systems across two-thirds of the provinces. [Rushton et al., \(2005\)](#) highlighted the lack of veterinary workforce, in countries such as LAO PDR, as critical factor responsible for lack of reporting and indicated the need for future investments on this, while at the same time stressing the importance of investment to facilitate restructure of the industry and integration of health systems to better detect and tackle the control of epidemics. Several countries reported AC parameters related to upgrades in farm and market biosecurity infrastructure. In Türkiye, many farmers were supported and encouraged to invest into strengthening biosecurity after the 2006 outbreak by providing low interest loans by the government ([Yalçın, 2006](#)). [Hinrichs and Sims \(2006\)](#) described approximately 7 million smallholders in Vietnam and the cost of training; even 10% at an assumed cost of \$50 per farm would be \$35 million training costs for the government.

Tax revenue losses and GDP reductions (ICC) are acknowledged in many studies remained comparatively under-documented. The British Columbia outbreak indicated 86% of poultry farm tax payments were delayed ([Bowes, 2007](#)). Similarly, the Turkish government reported government expenditure of 31.7 million YTL to combat HPAI disease and compensate the industry, however induced losses in production and therefore tax revenue. The postponement of tax of the industry was for 6 months and loss figures were not provided ([Yalçın, 2006](#)).

This pattern suggests a geographic bias and reflecting differences in economic assessment priorities as well as the prominence of informal economic sectors in LMICs. Nevertheless, such losses may be particularly consequential in LMICs regions who rely heavily on Agricultural GDP and gross regional product (GRP) significantly for economic sustainability and growth. Illustrative examples of these impacts are well documented in several studies from the United States. A simulation study in Mississippi, USA, estimated tax revenue losses of \$55,117 from poultry export bans and \$276,108 from a 1.2 million-broiler decline linked to production and export restrictions ([Myles et al., 2009](#)). In

Iowa, HPAI outbreaks led to estimated federal tax (including personal income tax, sales tax, property tax, corporate profit taxes, motor vehicles taxes, and excise taxes) losses of \$97.9 million and state and local tax losses of \$47.2 million in 2014 ([Decision Innovation Solutions, 2015b](#)). At a national level, HPAI outbreaks involving layers were estimated to result in losses of \$248.6 million in federal taxes and \$136.1 million in state and local taxes ([Decision Innovation Solutions, 2015a](#)).

The NFI are centred on erosion of trust in government and communication failures, [Alders et al. \(2014\)](#) detailed that, in village settings, one of the most significant negative impacts of HPAI control efforts was the use of communication materials poorly suited to local contexts. This mismatch undermined the credibility of technical recommendations among producers and traders. The issue stemmed from earlier HPAI outbreaks, when prevention and control guidelines were designed for the intensive commercial poultry industry and were not adequately adapted for rural areas. This inappropriate extension of materials undermined credibility, suggesting that process quality matters as much as resource allocation.

3.4.3. Public health impacts

The public health sector ([Fig. 7](#)) presented a starkly different profile, with NFI constituting 56% of identified parameters, the highest proportion across all sectors. However, 21/23 NFI parameters were only found in articles from LMICs and 63% of total parameters in this sector were identified from LMICs literature. This suggests that HPAI impacts different countries in different ways depending on their industry context and health risks. For examples small-scale farming context leads to visible human suffering when affected by HPAI, therefore making NFIs harder to ignore. Countries with more limiting infrastructure, and regulatory and enforcement procedures, seem to be experiencing more human cases and difficulties and consequently increase NFIs and overall public health impacts. Several studies looked at lost income due to illness, particularly in contexts where individuals must miss work,

Fig. 7. Illustration a section of the economic framework which categorises the impacts into direct costs (medical expenditure, personal and business losses, reduced quality of life), direct consequential costs, indirect consequential costs (preventing spread revenue foregone due to trade restrictions, increased expenditure from supply shortages), aftermath costs (long-term medical expenses), and non-financial impacts of public health. It also highlights non-financial impacts, including gender and nutritional impacts, welfare issues, consumer behavioural change, food safety risks, cultural disruptions, and social instability in affected communities. DALY=disability adjusted life year. PRC=polymerase chain reaction.Theoretical, E: Empirical, B: Benefit, * LMIC only, ** HIC only.

alongside out-of-pocket expenses incurred for accessing healthcare services, such as travel to medical facilities (Humphries-Waa et al., 2013). In Cambodia, Humphries-Waa et al. (2013) found that patients had to travel an average of 148 kilometres (8–476 km) to the admitting hospital when affected with HPAI. This accounted not only distance travelled but also the quality of the roads. In two cases, border crossings to Vietnam, were reported due to possible distrust of public services (to receive better medical treatment) and a desire to avoid the associated user charges. Pam et al. (2022) investigated the psychosocial effects associated from HPAI in Nigeria during the 2006–2007 which found that affected farmers were stressed, anxious and severely depressed. These symptoms would affect other aspects of life like work productivity levels and hostility within society. In addition, economic burden may arise from chronic disability like depression or suicide which can reduce earning potential (Pam et al., 2022). Such long-term health conditions and depression have received limited attention despite the potential overshadowing of immediate medical costs. Measurable cost represented only a fraction of consequences in public health.

Parameters capturing NFI associated to social dynamics in LMICs were also prominent, spanning gender inequality, food insecurity, educational disruption, stigma and the violence against poultry keepers. These impacts exacerbates pre-existing socioeconomic vulnerabilities, including reduced decision making power among woman (Ahuja et al., 2009) girls migrating to exploitative labour (Alders et al., 2014), and coping strategies among poor households that involve reducing staple food consumption. For example, Geerlings (2007) conducted in Egyptian households, after HPAI outbreaks, some women were forced to withdraw their children from school because they could no longer afford fees or essential materials. This not only affected the children’s well-being but also harmed the women’s self-esteem, as it undermined their ability to provide for their households. In Murshidabad, in India (September–October 2007), following a HPAI outbreak the average rice consumption declined from 63 kg to 50 kg per month (Ahuja et al.,

2009) described cases where poultry keepers were wrongly accused of spreading HPAI, resulting in harassment (by the public and police), physical violence, and destruction of property e.g. baskets damaged, and chicks killed.

In terms of ICC, several parameters revolving around revenue loss due to change in trading and supply shortage which affect the consumer (e.g., reduced demand for poultry with increased demand and consequently, higher prices for alternative protein sources). Rushton et al. (2005) reported that following an HPAI outbreak in Cambodia in February 2004, prices of beef and pork increased markedly. These elevated prices persisted even after consumers resumed purchasing poultry products in March, indicating a sustained substitution effect. Similar trends were observed in Türkiye’s broiler sector experiencing rapid and recurrent disruptions from both disease outbreaks and market speculation between 1994–2006. Chicken meat supply was influenced by factors including fluctuations in the prices of substitute products such as beef and fish further exacerbated instability within the poultry supply chain (Aral, Demir, et al., 2010). Within the European Union, assessments projected a short-term increase in global meat prices following major outbreaks. This included a 7–8% increase in poultry and beef prices, and a 3% increase in pig meat prices. These market shifts were accompanied by reductions in global meat consumption and realignments in trade flows, with other markets stepping in to replace disrupted supply from Europe and Brazil. Spillover effects were also anticipated in feed markets, where reductions in meat production were expected to lower the demand for feed grains and protein meals by 1–2% (McLeod et al., 2005).

3.4.4. Other businesses

Business sectors show concentration in DCs with an absence of NFI and environment sector showing far less consideration than all other sectors (Fig. 8).

Several sectors were reported to be affected by HPAI, such as

Fig. 8. Details a section of the economic framework which categorises the impacts into direct costs, direct consequential costs, indirect consequential costs, aftermath costs, and non-financial impacts of other businesses and the environment. It includes direct costs such as payouts, debts, and revenue changes from sales, as well as indirect costs from supply shortages and reduced consumer demand. Aftermath costs include losses in tourism, real estate value, and price changes for inputs. Environmental impacts cover resource use, land value decline, and biodiversity loss, emphasizing the broader ecological and economic consequences of HPAI outbreaks. Theoretical, E: Empirical, B: Benefit, * LMIC only, ** HIC only.

insurance companies, tourism and airlines. An economic impact assessment conducted in the USA (Iowa) in 2014 estimated the top ten industries affected by the HPAI outbreak, with collectively losses of approximately \$1.2 billion, and which included real estate, rail transportation and insurance carriers incurring combined losses of \$22 million (Decision Innovation Solutions, 2015b). Similarly, other sectors, such as airlines and high-leverage agricultural enterprises were financially affected and led to a surge in bankruptcies (Brahmbhatt, 2005). In India (Kerala), boat operators experienced a loss of \$2280 fall in tourism due to HPAI outbreak (2014) (Govindaraj et al., 2018). The article noted that boat cruise services, transport, hotel and entertainment services were also affected. Further, two papers expressed concerns about the impacts of HPAI outbreaks on Indonesia and Thailand, respectively, due to their reliance on tourism (Safman, 2009; McLeod et al., 2005).

In terms of ICC, some studies suggest that global market dynamics and competitive advantage changed. A simulation study by Djunaidi and Djunaidi (2007) demonstrated that a 25% reduction in poultry production in a major exporting country could lead to pronounced shifts in global trade patterns. For instance, in the event of an outbreak in Brazil, the average export price of poultry meat was projected to increase to \$894.8 per metric ton, a rise of \$8.6 above baseline prices.

3.4.5. Environment impacts

The environmental section reveals a critical and often overlooked blind spot, displaying the sparsest set of parameters across all sectors and with no DC identified. The absence likely reflects not a lack of environmental impacts, but rather the systematic exclusion of environmental considerations in HPAI economic assessments.

This section captures impact associated to waste management issues, natural resource concerns and biodiversity loss. Yet quantification of impacts remains rare. Outbreaks were reported to place increased pressure on waste management infrastructure due to mass culling events, which result in heightened demand for landfill space (Thompson and Pendel, 2016). The extensive use of disinfectants, water, and fuel in outbreak control operations further raised questions about the sustainability of natural resource use and the potential for environmental degradation, particularly in communities already experiencing water scarcity. A study by Robert et al. (2016) conducted in the USA noted a decline in land values associated with HPAI outbreaks.

The ecological impacts were prominent, for example, Gamarra-Toledo et al. (2023) study reports losses of marine bird species, including the Humboldt penguin, red-legged cormorant, and Peruvian booby and mortality rates among Peruvian pelicans in protected coastal areas were estimated at 13.4–25.3% with the associated interruption of nutrient deposition from guano-producing seabirds resulting in broader implications for coastal ecosystem health. Highlighting genetic erosion in poultry populations, particularly the loss of indigenous breeds posing

risks to poultry resilience and agricultural biodiversity. Other studies conducted across the UK highlight similar trends of loss of biodiversity and reduced breeding success. Coffey and Verspoor (2025) study conducted in Wales (2023) determined 9% of adult Black-headed Gulls and 1226 chicks were found dead, reducing fledglings count from 1250 (2022) to 75–100 (2023). 2024 breeding season implied a 75% reduction of breeding Common Terns, after accounting for natural mortality. The study further suggested the lack of action plan and decision-making delays resulted in carcasses remaining uncollected and an additional 378 dead adults and 376 dead chicks. Tremlett et al. (2024) found the Great Skua suffered the worst UK decline to 73% (2909) in occupied areas in 2023.

3.5. Economic methods

Table 11 provides an overview of methods used in the articles review. A combination of primary, secondary and expert opinion data was used across studies. In 15 papers, the methods description did not have enough detail to determine data collection methods used. Approximately 40% of articles described the use of secondary data, 37.5% of articles used primary data, 7.5% used a mixture of sources and 15% were not clearly described. Thirteen economic methods were identified with the most frequent being cost only analysis (20%) and cost-benefit analysis (11.25%) followed by partial equilibrium analysis (7.5%) and econometric analysis (5%). Fifteen articles used qualitative research, and another fifteen articles did not provide enough information to determine the methods used.

3.6. Quality assessment

Of the 85 papers subjected to the quality assessment, none included all 27 parameters (Table 12). Overall, there was good reporting in introductory and result sections, but gaps were found in methodological detail, sensitivity analysis and costing transparency and justification. Studies described the target populations well and economic perspectives. 40% of the articles did not detail the method of economic assessment. About 56% of articles justified the reasoning for analysis performed. Data limitations, models and assumptions often remained unclear. Sensitivity analysis was included in 9.41% of studies whilst currency adjustments and cost conversions were poorly reported in 35.29% and 34.12%, respectively.

4. Discussion

This review summarises economic impact estimates of HPAI outbreaks from various contexts worldwide based on historical outbreaks, simulation models and professional estimates. It further illustrates the

Table 11
Methods used in articles.

Section	Characteristics	No. studies	Section	Characteristics	No. Studies
Type of economic data analysed	Primary	35	Economic methods	Cost analysis	14
	Secondary	32		Cost-benefit analysis	9
	Mixed sources	6		Partial equilibrium analysis	6
	Not well specified	12		Econometric analysis	5
Type of epidemiological data analysed	Primary	11		Market chain analysis	2
	Secondary	37		General equilibrium analysis	1
	Mixed sources	5		Epi-economic model	2
	Not well specified	31		Multiple methods	3
	Literature	1		Rapid market analysis	2
				Theoretical supply and demand analysis	2
				Gross margin analysis	1
				Value chain analysis	1
				Spatial equilibrium analysis	1
				Fixed-Effects model	1
				Not applicable	20
			Not described	15	

Table 12
The framework used for appraising the quality of economic analyses of HPAI economic impacts.

Section	Component (Maximum score)	Quality parameter	No of papers	(%)	
Title	Title (1)	Provide a title that reflects the economic study on Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza.	69	81.18	
Abstract	Abstract (1)	Provide a structured summary outlining the context, key methods, and main results.	83	97.65	
Introduction	Context (1)	State clearly the study's context and justification.	84	98.82	
	Aims (1)	Define the study aims and emphasise their economic relevance.	73	85.88	
Method	Target population (2)	Describe the characteristics of the population and any subgroups analysed.	75	88.24	
		Explain the importance of the selected subtype in relation to the study.	72	84.71	
	Study design (4)	Describe the methods used to assess or estimate economic impact.	51	60.00	
		Justify the need for conducting the study.	48	56.47	
		Specify the perspective from which economic impact is analysed (e. g., business, public health).	65	76.47	
	Time horizon (1)	Explain the key assumptions in the analysis (including data sources and limitations).	51	60.00	
		Describe the time horizon(s) used for assessing costs and consequences.	60	70.59	
	Data Collection (3)	Describe the data sources (noting whether they are primarily primary or secondary data, and the extent to which they are based on observations versus expert opinion or assumptions).	Identify the economic indicators used to measure impact (e.g., income, GDP).	46	54.12
			Conduct and describe a sensitivity analysis.	8	9.41
Currency, price date, and conversion (3)		Report the dates of the estimated resource quantities and unit costs.	43	50.59	
		Describe methods for adjusting estimated unit costs to the year	30	35.29	

Table 12 (continued)

Section	Component (Maximum score)	Quality parameter	No of papers	(%)
Result	Findings (2)	of reported costs, if necessary. Describe methods for converting costs into a common currency and specify the exchange rate used.	29	34.12
		Report clearly the results of the economic impact, including both qualitative and quantitative findings.	72	84.71
Discussion	Recommendations, Implications and Limitation(5)	Report the results of the sensitivity analysis.	7	8.24
		Summarise recommendations arising from the study.	51	60.00
Other	Source of funding (1)	Interpret the economic impact in relation to the study objectives.	59	69.41
		Explain the implications for different stakeholders.	51	60.00
	Conflict of interest (1) Ethical approval (1)	Conclude with statements that support the study's findings.	78	91.76
		Discuss the limitations of the study and the generalisability of its findings.	38	44.71
		Describe how the study was funded and the funder's role in the design, conduct, and reporting.	53	62.35
		Disclose any conflicts of interest.	25	29.41
		Describe the ethical approval process, where applicable, for primary data collection.	6	7.06

diversity of parameters used in economic impact articles in a structured impact framework, further describes reporting and methodological rigor for HPAI. This synthesis reveals both the considerable scale of HPAI's economic burden and critical systematic gaps in how it has been measured, with important implications for prevention policy and resource allocation.

4.1. Total impact and relevance

Reported economic impact varied widely across countries and regions, ranging from \$1.14 million (USA, New York) to \$3.88 billion (Nigeria, 2015), affecting a variety of species and numerous sectors. The upper estimate makes this impact comparable to malaria (\$4.3 billion in 2016) and Foot and Mouth Disease (approximately 6.5–21 billion) (Knight-Jones and Rushton, 2013; Haakenstad et al., 2019). The lower estimate is comparable to Johnne's disease overall loss of £ 1.61 million per year for Scotland (SEFARI, 2018). This reflects the economic impact that HPAI has created over the past 100 years, gradually increasing in economic consequence. However, these figures fundamentally underestimate the true burden, as a magnitude of studies do not consider

multiple sectors and remain siloed either towards economic gains or individual sectors. As research has developed, it has become clear that the scope of impacts extends beyond a single industry, with areas such as the environment and retail businesses neglected and therefore left unaccounted within quantification efforts. While aggregated figures underscores the global scale of HPAI's economic burden, they mask important disparities in how these costs are distributed and measured across context, income levels and cost categories.

Differences in government responses and NFIs were evident between HICs and middle income countries (MICs). In HICs, the impacts of HPAI tended to be more evenly distributed across sectors, whereas in MICs the burden fell disproportionately on public health systems and local communities. In several MICs, expected government compensation payments were delayed or unmet, leading to bankruptcies and increased borrowing loans (Kanamori and Jimba, 2007). These failures eroded trust in authorities and undermined compliance with control measures. For example, Omiti and Okuthe (2009) found that in Kenya, perceived production risks led a quarter of farmers to engage in panic slaughter of broiler flocks. This behaviour appears linked to strict market specifications for minimum slaughter weights, which heighten the risk of holding birds during uncertain times.

From a behavioural economics perspective, such decisions reflect both risk aversion and loss aversion: farmers prefer a smaller, guaranteed return to the possibility of losing their entire flock. Social influence reinforces this tendency; observing peers cull early strengthens the belief that immediate cash flow outweighs potential long-term gains.

Similar patterns may emerge in low income countries (LICs) facing comparable constraints. In LICs with recurrent HPAI outbreaks, financial instability often leads to weaker adherence to regulations on animal destruction and disposal, further exacerbating disease spread. While this study did not identify formal economic assessments of HPAI in LICs, several factors likely contribute to prolonged outbreaks in these contexts, including limited veterinary infrastructure, insufficient research funding, constrained surveillance capacity, and heavy dependence on poultry for livelihoods. These conditions can delay containment and increase the risk of cross-border transmission.

Weaknesses in outbreak control in LICs have implications far beyond national borders. HPAI has spread to even the most remote regions of the world through trade, migration, and wildlife vectors. Notably, Antarctic, long free from infection, reported its first cases on 23 October 2023 (SCAR AWHN, 2024). Since then, millions of seabirds have suffered severe losses, with mortality rates reaching 50–60% in Gannets and Great Skuas, and tens of thousands of pinnipeds have died.

Despite such widespread ecological damage, economic assessments remain incomplete. To date, no systematic analyses have quantified the monetary value of wildlife mortality or the broader consequences for ecosystems. Likewise, other NFIs, such as impacts on food and nutrition security or loss of education, have rarely been quantified. Of the 108 countries across five continents affected by H5N1 (United Nations, 2024), many have no available economic impact studies. Even in Europe, where 31 countries have detected HPAI A(H5N1), only four have conducted economic assessments (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2025).

The available case studies highlight the scale of underestimation. In Nigeria, the 2014–2016 outbreak affected 276,675 incomes at \$4.14 per capita (Figs. 3 and 4), with costs reported for the poultry industry, government compensation, and vaccination, but little mention of consumer or environmental impacts (Fasanmi et al., 2018). In Thailand (2004), the outbreak affected 445,082 incomes at \$36.81 per capita (Figs. 3 and 4), but excluded government compensation expenditures, public health costs, and consumer effects (NaRanong, 2008). In both cases, the omission of key cost categories means the actual impacts were likely far greater than reported.

4.2. Findings of impact framework

This framework demonstrates that HPAI incurs extensive costs that extend beyond immediate outbreak control spanning across economic, social, and public health sectors, many of which are under-recognised in existing literature. By integrating DCs, DCCs, ICCs, ACs and NFIs, it advances previous farm-level models and provides a policy-relevant One Health lens for HPAI.

The framework highlights a recognition bias; DCs such as culling and disposal are more consistently acknowledged than DCCs, particularly within movement restriction zones. While monetary impacts on the poultry industry and government are well documented, community-level effects, public health burdens, business losses, and environmental damage, especially when borne by the public, are underexplored. This underestimation shapes an incomplete view of the true economic burden at both farm and regional levels.

Direct consequential costs, indirect consequential costs and non-financial impacts are particularly underreported when it comes to quantifying economic impact. One possible reason is that these costs are difficult to quantify, increase drastically the complexity of the economic assessment and necessitating a range of economic expertise (e.g. ecological economics methods would be needed to assess impact in biodiversity). Many of the DCC and ICC may require understanding of system changes in the industry or government structures or may make the necessity of data difficult to obtain. For example, the economic impact of movement restriction zones in LMICs may be challenging as it often involves porous enforcement that exist theoretically but function inconsistently and may cross borders; or the economic impact of informal sector (e.g. slaughterhouses, traders and farmers operating at small-scale without licensing or registration) may be missed given the lack of data. Further research comparing formal vs. informal sector impacts in the same outbreak would help distinguish underreporting of cost from genuinely different cost distributions.

Country-level differences in outbreak management illustrate these disparities. In HICs, like the UK, culling and disposal are typically managed and funded by government authorities. In the USA and some other cases, private companies (e.g., Patriot Environmental) carry out these operations. In countries, such as Kenya and India, the responsibility falls to farmers, who may resort to burial or manual suffocation. Where financial or operational capacities are lacking, consequences can escalate, leading to environmental contamination or increased selling of sick birds in wet markets, as documented in Vietnam (Delabougliše et al., 2016). Without structured support, some farmers turn to informal or illegal markets, further amplifying disease spread.

While compensation schemes such as the USDA (2025) expanded payments for HPAI losses have aided recovery in some contexts, many farmers, predominantly LMICs, receive little to no support and resort to personal loans, deepening financial strain (Rushton et al., 2005; Bowes, 2007; Myles et al., 2009; Yalcin et al., 2009; Aral, Yalcin, et al., 2010; Aengwanich, 2014; Johnson et al., 2016; Cakir et al., 2017). Few studies quantify the indirect impacts of informal and illegal poultry trade, whereby infected birds are sold cheaply to low-income consumers (Yang et al., 2023) increasing infection risk (Food Standards Agency et al., 2023) and undermining consumer confidence, market stability, and tourism.

Another key finding is the neglect of NFIs particularly broader societal effects in economic studies. Many articles acknowledge shifts toward alternative protein consumption but overlook the consequences of rising prices for these substitutes. Likewise, gendered impacts on food security, nutrition, and household behaviour, such as rationing, are rarely addressed. Supply shortages and price increases can disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, particularly women and girls who often manage small-scale poultry production (Diao et al., 2009; Ahuja et al., 2009; Limon et al., 2009). The loss of poultry removes a critical source of income, nutrition, and autonomy, eroding decision-making power and social recognition, and pushing communities toward

deeper marginalisation. Sometimes, these triggers reduced access to healthcare and education, early school withdrawal for children, and heightened risks of harmful practices such as forced marriage. Psychological distress from the loss of identity and stability is another under-addressed consequence.

This research future finds that impacts also vary by outbreak type. When HPAI affects humans, the economic and social costs expand dramatically. Few studies integrate costs from historical zoonotic transmission, yet such scenarios would impose substantial additional burdens, in LMICs where healthcare costs fall to individuals and access to services is limited. Public health repercussions can cascade into secondary costs, such as school closures that transfer childcare and feeding responsibilities back to households, compounding existing vulnerabilities. By mapping these diverse cost types, this framework supports a fuller understanding of the cost–benefit balance of interventions and strengthens the case for preventive investments.

This framework shares the similar component of core outbreak costs logic used in prior HPAI and animal health economic models; breaking impacts into categories such as DCs, DCCs, ICC and ACs (Longworth et al., 2014; Saatkamp et al., 2016). HPAI economic evaluations have largely focused on immediate, quantifiable impacts such as culling and disposal costs, compensation to farmers, and short-term trade losses (Otte, 2008; McLeod et al., 2005). Like earlier frameworks, it identifies costs to production, trade, disease control, and livelihoods, and recognises financial implications. Otte (2008) and Rushton's (2009) frameworks have looked at livestock diseases from a farm-system, context-specific lens which focused on losses at the farm-level and market. Whereas this framework explicated looks at the poultry industry and the connectivity towards government municipalities, public, consumer impacts, which adds several new perspectives viewing different contexts and a clearer lens into NFIs, rather than broader livestock disease frameworks.

While some studies acknowledged secondary effects, such as market disruptions or reduced consumer demand, these were typically underdeveloped, and social or cultural consequences were rarely considered beyond anecdotal mention. The framework presented advances this literature by providing a comprehensive, structured and expanding the definition and categorisations of costs, including NFIs, whilst explicitly integrates long-term societal effects which has yet been done previously. By incorporating response, preparedness and prevention expenditures, the framework bridges veterinary, economic, and human health perspectives within a One Health, offering a more holistic and policy-relevant tool than earlier, sector-specific models. Therefore, economic parameters are looked at collaboratively as each sector influences others. This broader scope not only captures hidden costs of HPAI often omitted from prior analyses but also enables more accurate cost–benefit evaluations of interventions aimed at prevention, control, and resilience building.

The impact of HPAI would exponentially increase should HPAI become transmissible between humans and result in a pandemic. Given the already considerable impact of HPAI and the concern over future epidemics and possibly pandemics with even wider reaching impacts (FAO and WOAHA (2025)), there is a case for investing in the prevention of HPAI through timely, coordinated, and collaborative efforts and investments that allow strengthening biosecurity infrastructure, implement effective vaccination programmes, and address the NFI of the disease through inclusive policies and stakeholder engagement. This risk underscores the critical importance of sustained surveillance, rapid response capacity, and coordinated policy interventions to mitigate both current outbreaks and the possibility of future epidemics with far-reaching socio-economic impacts.

Current initiatives provide a strong foundation for such action. The Pandemic Fund supports countries and regions in building preparedness and response capacity, including for zoonotic diseases such as HPAI, by financing interventions that strengthen surveillance systems, laboratory networks, and rapid response mechanisms (The Pandemic Fund, 2025).

Complementing this, the Quadripartite (FAO, WHO, WOAHA, and UNEP) Global Strategy for the Prevention and Control of H5N1 HPAI, and its earlier Tripartite framework, offers a coordinated, One Health based approach, emphasising risk reduction at the animal–human–environment interface, harmonised global surveillance, and rapid containment (FAO and WOAHA, 2025). Together, these efforts highlight the importance of sustained investment and cross-sectoral collaboration to mitigate current threats and avert future crises.

4.3. Methodological limitations in existing literature

There was a marked inconsistency in the reporting and methodological rigor of economic impact assessments related to HPAI outbreaks. A substantial proportion of the reviewed articles failed to apply standard economic parameters when calculating economic impact making it difficult to draw comparisons across studies, regions, or outbreak events. Many lacked a clear explanation of the economic methods applied and there was considerable variation among those that described methods in full. These methodological inconsistencies such as valuation techniques, cost categorisation, and assumptions regarding market prices, further impeded the aggregation and comparison of findings. Leading to variation in how costs are calculated and reported, hindering the identification of clear patterns of geographies and production systems.

Challenges are exacerbated by a lack of high-quality, comprehensive data. Studies fail to capture essential parameters, such as outbreak duration, production system type, or the scale of affected poultry populations, or present data in fragmented, non-comparable formats. In some cases, critical cost categories, including indirect and intangible impacts, are missing entirely, while in others, figures are collected in ways that obscure the underlying assumptions. For example, Akunzule et al. (2009) describes the different cost categories which impacted by HPAI, “Price of maize was reduced (by 36.6%); unsold maize incurred revenue losses” affecting 1 million farmers costing \$664 million. This figure was negated from the abstract of the study but also no clear explanation was provided for this inclusion of an economic assessment. Many studies lack transparency in how economic costs or total losses were derived. This absence in reporting has led to overestimations within some industries and underestimation in others, of effects of HPAI and prevents understanding between different contents and makes it more difficult for policymakers and donors to make evidence-based decisions.

Data gaps are particularly acute in LMICs where surveillance, diagnostic, and record-keeping systems may be weak or inconsistently funded. As a result, modelling efforts often rely on extrapolations from incomplete datasets, which can distort estimates and reduce their credibility. These limitations delay the development of accurate, locally relevant economic models and weaken the case for targeted investments in prevention, control, and recovery. Data within areas which are more sustainable and at higher risk to HPAI outbreaks are required to further the true impact of HPAI. Without robust and transparent data collection, the true scale and complexity of HPAI's economic and social burden remain obscured, perpetuating under preparedness and inequitable responses.

A significant limitation in current HPAI economic assessments is the lack of up-to-date, region-specific data on poultry population sizes, agricultural gross regional product (AgGRP), human population and regional salary, which are essential for accurately estimating present-day impacts. Most articles focused on regional areas or rural towns therefore when national-level statistics are used to calculate common denominators the impact per capita or for the area is much more widely distributed than saturated into the specific locality. This significantly underpins the effect of HPAI outbreaks on the local regions. The absence of AgGRP limits the ability to contextualise HPAI's impact within the broader economic landscape, obscuring its proportional effect on local livelihoods and economies. Consequently, present-day values are often underestimated reducing the precision and relevance of findings for

decision-makers, donors, and policymakers tasked with allocating resources and designing targeted interventions.

Furthermore, without granular, up-to-date data, economic losses are often modelled using assumptions that may no longer reflect reality, leading to distorted valuations. The use of outdated data is particularly problematic in regions where poultry production has expanded or contracted significantly in recent years due to shifts in demand, disease outbreaks, or policy changes. Thus, outdated simulation models to predict the effects of future pandemics.

To improve the reliability and comparability of HPAI economic assessments, standardised reporting frameworks and greater transparency on cost reporting are urgently needed. Current studies vary widely in the types of costs included- such as whether transportation of culled stock is counted; leading to gaps, biases, and underestimation of disease burden. Minimum reporting standards should capture parameters like year of analysis, poultry population size, production system type, outbreak duration, the economic methodology and the source where economic costs were captured. Many existing studies contain incomplete or hard-to-extract data, limiting cross-case synthesis.

Future research should prioritise methodological clarity, structured gap analyses of cost occurring in poultry contexts, and alignment with standardised frameworks to ensure overlooked direct costs, direct consequential costs, indirect consequential costs, aftermath costs and non-financial impacts, such as veterinary services, environmental impacts, and pharmaceutical interventions.

Transparency regarding production and communication costs for vaccines and antivirals, for both humans and animals is vital for preparedness, response equity, and sustainable control strategies. Without integrating these costs into regional, national and international plans, reliance on less sustainable and ethical measures like culling persists, particularly in resource-limited settings, further widening global health disparities. Strengthening methodological foundations will bridge the gap between scientific evidence and actionable policy, guiding targeted, cost-effective, and equitable disease control.

These methodological weaknesses undermine global abilities to apprehend HPAI's true economic burden and design appropriate interventions.

4.4. Limitations of review

The review followed strict PRISMA guidelines and a significant effort was done to capture as many publications as possible on the economics of HPAI. Yet, it is possible that some relevant articles, particularly non-English reports done by some institutions, may have been missed. We reviewed the first 200 results in google scholar as recommended by [Hughes et al. \(2014\)](#) and [Roe et al. \(2014\)](#) and thus we expect to have captured the large majority of these reports.

The review did not allow to conduct any statistical analysis or meta-analysis due to the substantial heterogeneity in study design, cost categories, outcome definitions, and analytical approaches of existing literature. This methodological diversity limits the validity of pooled estimates and generalised cross-country and cross-sector comparisons, requiring that economic impacts of HPAI be interpreted as context-specific rather than universally. The use of unvalidated AI for translation also causes limitations for capturing literature sources.

5. Conclusions

This review provides a comprehensive understanding of the different impacts that HPAI has on many different levels of society and documents the magnitude of the burden worldwide. It highlights the need to enhance the comparability of impact estimates through more standardisation and transparency; the framework developed could be a reference point for this.

The comprehensive and structured overview of the many parameters that determine the economic impact of HPAI can be considered by

researchers and decision-makers during the planning and preparation stages of HPAI control and be used as a tool when estimating (baseline) impacts or conducting economic assessments of HPAI mitigation strategies.

The findings from this study highlight the need for targeted mitigation measures that addresses not only the economic and social costs to humans but the broader impact on society. This includes effects on poultry, other livestock and non-livestock species, the role of non-industry sectors, and often overlooked or hidden costs. A comprehensive and transparent approach is essential to fully capture the true burden of the disease, both for policy development and future research. Strengthening economic methodologies and incorporating sociocultural dimensions into disease impacts and decision making for control will be critical to ensure effective and fair strategies that consider local realities.

To further advance this field of research, the proposed impact framework should be applied to economic assessment of HPAI outbreaks (post-2015), to improve relevance and comparability. Economic parameters should be included based on relevance of the context studied. There is a clear need to develop robust methodologies for quantifying NFIs, which affect not only on the most vulnerable but also the well-equipped. These impacts include psychosocial, environmental, ecological, gendered which remain significantly underrepresented in existing studies across all contexts. Finally, greater transparency and methodological standardisation in reporting economic data for HPAI outbreaks is essential, this includes clear definitions, cost categorisation, methodological assumptions and justifications all of which is essential to strengthening evidence synthesis to support well-informed policy responses. For policymakers, the administration of this framework supports a holistic, evidence-based decision-making process by explicitly considering cross-sectional trade-offs, distributional impacts and long-term social consequences when prioritising prevention methods (education and biosecurity) and control methods (culling/vaccination/movement restrictions).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Barbara Häslér: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Zahraa Nisaa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Pablo Alarcon:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Francesca Scolamacchia:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Raquel Jorquera:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Houda Bennani:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

There was no conflict of interest during this research. No ethical approval was needed to conduct this research.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.prevetmed.2026.106827](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2026.106827).

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